

Indian Public Health Standards and Human Resources Requirements

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ABSTRACT:

Context: The government of India in the Ministry of Health & Family Welfare adopted *Indian Public Health Standards* in place of the *Bureau of Indian Standards*. The aim was to provide simpler norms to set up new and upgradation of existing health facilities, workforce required, and kind of services ensured in the country through the National Rural Health Mission despite several deficiencies in the terms of number of facilities and workforce evident.

Aims and objectives: Analysis of the pros and cons of inadequate coverage could be the main aims and objectives of this paper.

Methods and Material: Identification of gaps in terms of several facilities, workforce, and logistics done under the premises of materials such as '*Rural Health Survey Bulletins*', '*MIS on NRHM*', '*Census 2011*', and '*Indian Public Health Standards*'. In addition, almost 100 case studies of health facilities in different states were performed.

Results: A shortfall of approximately 100914 Health Sub Centers or HSCs, 17399 Primary Health Centers or PHCs, 5728 Community Health Centers or CHCs, and 1476 Sub Divisional Hospital or First Referral Units or FRUs in the country. The workforce required to run these facilities is also hugely deficient. Such data further revealed that approximately 40.7 percent, 42.36 percent, 55.77 percent, and 60.99 percent populations of the country are not covered by any Health Sub Centers, Primary Health Centers, Community Health Centers, and Sub Divisional Hospitals or First Referral Units respectively.

Conclusions: Indian Public Health Standards not properly implemented. Although several states geared up to set up new health facilities and gradation existing health facilities to the tune of IPHS despite lack of workforce emerged main hindrance and this was acknowledged by authorities from time to time.

Key messages: It required to produce, acquire, develop, and retain a workforce in adequate numbers and expansion and setting up health facilities according to the existing workforce either in the health department or in the market before ensuring this investment in infrastructure or logistics would be waste, as this research observed.

Keywords: National Rural Health Mission; Indian Public Health Standards; Rural Health Survey; Public Health Workforce in India.

Full texts:

1. Introduction:

National Rural Health Mission or NRHM a flagship initiative of the Government of India intended to reformation of the public health system, was launched in April 2005 throughout the country and remained operative until March 2012^[1].

The Indian public health system was found deficient in terms of both quality of services and adequacy of coverage. The chief reasons identified included deficient workforce, logistics, and infrastructure. To overcome deficiencies in terms of workforce, logistics, and infrastructure the Government of India in the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare adopted norms of Indian Public Health Standards or IPHS. The earlier draft format of IPHS was released in the year 2006 while the revised draft was released in the year 2010. IPHS sets norms for facilities required to be set up based on population criteria and the range of services at each health facility starting from health sub-centers or HSCs to District Hospitals or DHs. Norms for Primary Health Centers or PHCs, Community Health Centers or CHCs, and divisional Health Centers are also outlined ^{[2] [3] [4] [5]}. Thus,

the IPHS formed the basis for establishing new health facilities and upgrading existing health facilities in the country under NRHM.

Health care delivery in India is envisaged at three levels namely primary, secondary, and tertiary. At the primary level HSCs and PHCs are required to set up every 5000 and 30000 population however this population limit was further lower to a level of 3000 and 20000 for hilly/ tribal and hard-to-reach areas. The secondary level of health care essentially included Community Health Centres or CHCs, constituting the First Referral Units (FRUs) and the District hospitals. The CHCs are designed to provide referral health care for cases from the primary level and cases in need of specialist care approaching the center directly. Each CHC thus required catering to approximately 80,000 populations in tribal/hilly areas and 1, 20,000 populations in plain areas. CHC would be a 30-bed hospital providing specialist care in medicine, Obstetrics and Gynecology, Surgery, and Pediatrics. These centers however fulfilling the tasks entrusted to them only to a limited extent. The launch of the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) allowed having a fresh look at their functioning. NRHM envisaged bringing up the CHC services to the level of Indian Public Health Standards. Although there were already existing standards as prescribed by the *Bureau of Indian Standards* for 30-bedded hospitals, those were at present not achievable as they are very resource-intensive. At the tertiary level regional, state-level specialty, and super specialty hospitals were required although no guidelines were yet outlined for the tertiary level under IPHS.

The problem:

The key problem this paper opted to highlight is that the coverage of health facilities never corresponded to the population norms prescribed. Even so much so that the number of facilities, and work workforce required is not assessed properly by the Ministry of Health & FW as clear from the data assessed from the websites www.mohfw.nic.in/nrhm ^[6]. Rural Health Survey done by the Ministry of Health and FW, GOI published such reports, which were not justifiable as they contained false figures in terms of number of workforce and facilities required as per IPHS. They are not based upon the IPHS revised draft 2010 and census 2011.

According to the revised draft of the Indian Public Health Standards published in the year 2010, it required setting up health sub-centers per 5000 population in plain areas and 3000 population in the hilly/ tribal and hard-to-reach areas. The same draft also suggested in clear terms that one primary health center required setting up for each 30000 population in the plain areas and 20000 populations in the hilly/ tribal or hard-to-reach areas. Similarly, the draft had said that community health centers were required to be set up for each 80000 population in hilly/ tribal and hard-to-reach areas and 120000 populations in plain areas. Sub-divisional hospital of First referral units required setting up for each 5-6 lakh population. Besides this, each district required one district hospital to have several beds adjusted in tune with the population of the district. In addition, the number and kind of workforce required at each facility are also prescribed. Despite such a huge difference in terms of required health, facilities and workforce made the key problem under the research.

The gaps in infrastructure, workforce, and logistics analyzed in this research appeared much higher than the figures shown by the Government. It appeared that some states were not able to analyze and calculate the required number of facilities and workforce accurately therefore such a huge gap persisted according to this research. It would be evident that NRHM was implemented both in urban and rural areas since it earlier planned to launch a different health mission for urban areas but nothing happened and the services under NRHM were made to cover urban areas also. However, it appeared that the urban population was not considered by several states while calculating the required number of facilities in their states and they considered only the rural population resulting in a reduced number of facilities required in those states.

The problem of '*timing*' in the public health sector of India emerged after almost six years of implementation of the NRHM in the country according to this research. It observed that at several places breakdowns in existing public health care services including medical services occurred more frequently due to a lack of *timing* among the availability of the infrastructure, workforce, and logistics simultaneously. The health delivery system is so dependent on these three factors that *timing* among these three factors most crucial. The temporary or permanent breakdown of services was mainly due to the lack or absence of any one or two or even all three basic components either permanently or temporarily. An analysis of several breakdown situations established that all three components required running the public health delivery system round the clock such as workforce, infrastructure, and logistics not available simultaneously. There are several examples that if doctors are available then there are no supportive staff, if both doctors and supportive staff are available then there is no infrastructure or logistics.

The word 'timing' was conceptualized under this research to identify the level of readiness of the public health sector in India to deliver the desired health services at any point in time. Timing under the research literary taken as a situation where all the three major components required to make a health system functional like infrastructure, logistics, and workforce remain available round the clock simultaneously and concurrently, and if any components missing then it would cause a breakdown in the health services. The concept of 'timing' could apply differently under varied situations. The word 'timing' could have a different interpretation in the case of public health services or medical services separately but the moment we assume that medical services are also a part of any public health care system, it applies to both. Experiences and observations built under the research that precise *timing is required for both medical services and the public health services in the country*. *Timing* is not realized at several locations in the country due to deficiencies in terms of all three components or any one or two components. Lack of timing caused three kinds of breakdown in the health services casual, temporary, and permanent. The casual and temporary breakdown of the health services resulted due to the sudden emergence of deficiencies either in infrastructure, workforce, or logistics whereas permanent breakdown emerged due to the no expansion of coverage based on population norms suggested by IPHS as the population remained uncovered.

2. Aims and objectives:

This paper highlighted the inadequacy of public health coverage in the country. It found that several health facilities never by the requirements as per population norms prescribed by the IPHS. Therefore, a further aim of this paper might also be to analyze the reasons, actions, and remedies.

4. Methods and materials:

This paper is a partial derivative of the overall doctoral research in which the author engaged during 2009-12. The overall empirical research involved qualitative and quantitative methods of research. The paper is based upon the case studies involving almost 50 Health Sub Centers (HSCs), 34 Primary Health Centers (PHCs), and 10 District Hospitals (DHs) in several states like Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Uttar Pradesh, and West Bengal.

A comprehensive gap analysis for each state was conducted by the scholar based on the 2011 population with a motive to estimate the number of existing and required health facilities and workforce in the country according to the norms of IPHS. The gap analysis was done based on the norms provided by the Indian Public Health Standards. Then the existing workforce and infrastructure were identified from sources such as "Rural Health Survey Bulletins 2006, 2008" ^[6] and "MIS on NRHM June 2011" ^[7]. Finally, the viewpoints, observations, and suggestions put forward in the view of several kinds of literature, reports, and news clippings related to NRHM. Reports of all three Common Review Missions (CRMs) ^[8] were also considered.

The paper also reflected the essence of two sample surveys conducted by the scholar. Almost 600 persons belonging to different categories such as different age groups, BPL/ APL divide, gender, rural/urban divide, and from different states were questioned based on a structured questionnaire specifically designed for the purpose. The ranking was given to different questions and points were allocated such as 10 points for answers like highly agree, 6 points for somewhat agree, 3 points for somewhat disagree, and 0 point for disagree. A confidence level of more than 95% was maintained for predicting results. The matrix of sample surveys, case studies, and interviews could not be mentioned here, as they are part of overall doctoral research.

5. Results:

The gap analysis in the public health sector under this research could be a numerical expression of the deficiency, that existed between the availability and requirements of workforce, infrastructure, and logistics as per Indian Public Health Standards. For gap analysis, the population of the country and States/ UTs in the census 2011 were considered. On investigation, it found that a huge gap persisted even after more than six years of NRHM and its first tenure near completion with just 1-2 months left at the time of compiling this paper. The gap in several health facilities required and existing is identified and mentioned in tabular form in **Table-1**; therefore, you may please see **Table-1**.

It was evident from **Table 1** that there was a shortfall of approximately 100914 HSCs, 17399 PHCs, 5728 CHCs, and 1476 Sub Divisional or FRUs in the country. Such data said that approximately 40.7 percent, 42.36 percent, 55.77 percent, and 60.99 percent populations of the country are not covered by any Health Sub Centers, Primary Health Centers, Community Health Centers, and Sub Divisional Hospitals or First Referral Units respectively.

The required number of different kinds of workforce is estimated and presented in tabular form in **Table** and; therefore, please see in **table-2**. However, the number of existing workforces could not be retrieved despite all efforts. This showed the employee data was not properly maintained at the state level and central level though at the district level list could be available but collecting information from 644 districts of the country seemed not possible. Even the Rural Health Survey bulletin could not provide information on all kinds of existing employees. Several existing employees are presented in tabular form in **table-3**; therefore, see in **table-3**. I would recommend that public health employee data be maintained in the country properly and not only this it is easily assessable. In addition, the Rural Health Survey provided information for plain and tribal areas differently which is illogical.

6. Discussion:

Case studies revealed that there are numerous incidents across the country but more in the EAG States where infrastructure and logistics are not usable due to a lack of adequate workforce. At several places in EAG states buildings and logistics were created but not used to some or great extent due to lack of adequate workforce. Several health centers existed without women doctors or gynecologists. Health facilities found suffering due to a lack of surgeons and specialist doctors at the district and sub-district level hospitals. Therefore, it would be proper to ascertain the availability of medical and paramedical staff before planning for the upgrade and creation of infrastructure and logistics for health facilities. Only those facilities required to upgrade for which all kinds of the workforce could ensure. The crisis of doctors and paramedics was so steep that in several states doctors posted in the form of mobile mode and deputed to serve at several places. This could be an indicative that in most cases delivery of several services remained confined just to papers.

Therefore, the planning process under NRHM must correspond to the availability of the workforce. The workforce used to have legs also therefore they could migrate to other organizations more frequently and certain provisions required for the longevity of the attachment period of staff. In some states, provisions that doctors required to extend services in rural areas for a certain period despite many doctors not willing to post in rural areas and so much, they usually persuaded authorities to keep themselves posted at locations near urban centers. This could be because in several states urban health facilities had more doctors than required whereas in rural areas their number hugely fell short of than required. In primary health centers there, are hardly any residential quarters for staff and due to the lack of school electricity and poor law & order staff wished were not posted in rural or remote areas. In this manner, services could not extend to rural and remote areas. In addition, it found that there are hardly good doctors in the system. There were a handful of reputed doctors and their OPDs remained full of patients whereas several doctors engaged themselves in discharging clerical jobs. Nevertheless, high-serving doctors are not paid much in comparison to low-performing doctors thus some doctors are overburdened whereas several doctors have no work. However, multi-skilling of doctors was planned under NRHM but such training was not adequate and the services of those doctors who made to extend services other than their specialization lacked quality and thus were very vulnerable.

Until an adequate workforce is made available, planning and investments for new health installations could not be logical and it would be a huge waste of public funds. The numerical inadequacy of the workforce causes a shadow on the expansion of coverage of public health services in several states of India.

The gap in infrastructure and logistics could be filled at a given point in time but the gap in workforce medical and paramedical staff emerged as one of the most challenging factors. Several efforts were initiated or were in the pipeline to fill the gap in the workforce in the country. It will not be possible for the medical and paramedical institutions in India to fill the gap between doctors and paramedics for the next fifty years due to the paucity of resources and capacities. Therefore, the country embarking upon introducing new cadres in the medical field namely 'Bachelor of Rural Health' ^[9] which is expected to enable the services of doctors in rural areas in a short time. However, questions arise about whether would they call doctors even though some paramedic degrees are provided in more than three years. In addition, the capacity of the present workforce is planned improved by providing them with multi-skilling. Some medical services are outsourced to the private sector. In addition, the focus is put on setting up new medical and paramedical institutions in the country in the public or private sector.

The lack of *timing* among infrastructure, logistics, and workforce was responsible for most of the breakdown of the health services or decline in its quality in the country. The timing was not achievable mainly due to the lack of workforce in the country as prescribed by the IPHS. Infrastructure, logistics, or workforce without adequate timing could be useless. Making the workforce in adequate numbers requires more focus and for this purpose, more and more medical and paramedical institutions are required to be set up in the country at the

district level. In addition, it required addressing the discrepancies that existed in the health system such as dissimilar salaries for similar work, and different terms of service for evenly qualified persons.

The issue of *timing* applied in the case of both the existing and required health facilities of the country. In several states, many existing health facilities are not adequately manned, and adequate infrastructure and logistics are also not created. Several facilities were overcrowded and delivery of services was not adequate and found suffering from varied deficiencies. The number of OPD cases witnessed phenomenal growth in recent years but health services could not limit to just OPD services.

It is prescribed under NRHM to expand the coverage of health services as per population norms under IPHS. Facility surveys are conducted in the country to estimate the requirements of health facilities and to assess deficiencies in terms of workforce, infrastructure, or logistics in existing health facilities. Those health facilities needed gradation according to IPHS. Therefore, the focus under NRHM is definitely on the expansion of health services by facilitating all three components such as workforce, infrastructure, and logistics. Simultaneously the focus was also on increasing the number of health facilities as per IPHS norms. Nevertheless, all did not go well. However, funds were available infrastructure and logistics could create but challenge witnessed in the form of a lack of workforce. The lack of workforce especially doctors and paramedics could not level overnight and it required time because the capacity of the country to produce doctors and paramedics is so limited ^[10]. This halted the expansion process of health coverage and caused a lack of *timing*. Until and unless the required *timing* is obtained the public health, services would remain vulnerable.

It investigated that certain states were not able to extend the number of health installations according to their population though that was required accomplished as per IPHS. Thus, the coverage of health services in the public sector was never adequate in those states. It further investigated that this situation arises mainly due to a lack of adequate numbers of doctors and paramedics. Lack of workforce almost halted the expansion of public health facilities in the country and despite all efforts; the gap persisted in the workforce, infrastructure, and logistics, which required tapping to achieve precise timing among them in a sustained manner. In some states, especially poor-performing states this gap was so substantial that it required some special intervention in the form of sustained administrative efforts at various levels of administration.

It estimated that there was a shortfall of almost 0.7 million doctors in the country and this shortfall was so high that it was not possible to expand the coverage of health services to the tune of IPHS. This resulted in a situation where a large population remained uncovered or poorly serviced across the country but the problem could be more visible in those EAG states or highly focused states of the country. It is almost evident that this huge gap cannot leveled shortly either. The country since independence able to produce 0.6 million doctors approximately and filling the gap of more than 0.6 million doctors would consume a further fifty years. Therefore, a rationale concept was brought forward by the health planners to introduce a new cadre of doctors in the country namely '*Bachelor of Rural Health*'. It proposed that under this cadre, doctors would complete education within 3-4 years and their services might be available in a short period. Nevertheless, this idea generated widespread demonstrations and strikes, especially by the Indian Medical Association, which went all out opposing this new cadre in the country's health sector. Even after the tenure of NRHM about to complete nothing concrete advances on this issue could make light of the day.

Several provisions existed under NRHM for providing multi-skilling training to its existing workforce ^[11]. Multi-skilling could help to prevent any unwanted disruption in the services. Multi-skilling training of the workforce such as doctors, paramedics, and managerial staff was one of the most focused approaches under NRHM to tackle the issue of lack of workforce. Nevertheless, multi-skilling also had extremely limited usages and thus any extraordinary could not achieved by multi-skilling. Also, though multi-skilling appeared more prudent in developed states it was not such in EAG states. Under multi-skilling, doctors or paramedics trained for performing that kind of job, which could not be expected from them in ordinary situations, but extraordinary situations required extraordinary approaches. However, multi-skilling was useful and required despite it being a temporary arrangement and not any solution.

7. Conclusion:

The concept of *timing* for a public health sector used to occur simultaneously with all three factors force, infrastructure, and logistics all the time. With a huge gap persisting as per IPHS in terms of several required and existing health facilities and workforce the public health coverage could not be achieved adequately. The level of adequacy and coverage could much deficient as shown in the Rural Health Surveys. Either IPHS was

just a crude document or certain deficiencies existed in terms of implementing IPHS by the authorities. Confusing data shown by the Ministry of Health and FW GOI required perfection.

The government must assess the availability of the workforce first try to produce and acquire them first and then opt for expansion or upgrading of health facilities or the creation of new health facilities as per IPHS. Thus, IPHS just remained unimplemented in the country. It required investing, creating a workforce first, and then planning for expansion and up gradation of health facilities according to the available workforce. Infrastructure, logistics, and workforce in the absence of each other could prove precious waste of resources for a poor country. Unfortunately, NRHM is not able to do anything in this regard to produce, acquire, groom, and retail the workforce for the country's public health sector.

8. Acknowledgment:

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Table 1: Deficiencies in the number of facilities

S. No.	India/States/UTs	Total Population 2011	Health centers		Primary health centers		Community health centers		Sub- District hospitals		District hospitals	
			R*	E**	R*	E**	R*	E**	R*	E**	R*	E**
01	INDIA	1210193422	247943	147029	41072	23673	10269	4541	2420	944	644	645
02	J & K	12548926	4183	1907	627	375	157	85	25	00	22	22
03	Himachal#	6856509	2285	2071	343	449	86	73	14	36	12	12
04	Punjab	27704236	5540	2950	923	446	231	129	55	35	20	20
05	Chandigarh	1054686	211	16	35	00	9	02	2	00	1	1
06	Uttarakhand #	10116752	3372	1765	506	239	126	55	20	18	13	18
07	Haryana	25353081	5070	2444	845	441	211	107	51	25	21	21
08	NCT of Delhi	16753235	3350	41	558	08	140	00	33	49	9	18
09	Rajasthan	68621012	13724	11487	2287	1504	572	368	137	12	33	33
10	Uttar Pradesh	199581477	39916	20521	6652	3692	1663	515	399	00	75	134
11	Bihar	103804637	20760	9696	3460	1863	865	70	208	40	38	36
12	Sikkim#	607688	202	147	30	24	8	00	1	00	4	04
13	Arunachal #	1382611	461	286	69	97	17	48	3	00	16	14
14	Nagaland#	1980602	660	396	99	126	25	21	4	00	11	11
15	Manipur#	2721756	907	420	136	73	34	16	5	01	9	07
16	Mizoram#	1091014	364	370	54	57	14	09	2	2	8	8
17	Tripura#	3671032	1224	627	183	79	46	11	7	11	4	2
18	Meghalaya#	2964007	988	405	148	109	37	29	6	1	7	10
19	Assam	31169272	6233	4604	1039	856	260	108	62	13	27	22
20	West Bengal	91347736	18269	10356	3045	909	761	348	183	45	19	16
21	Jharkhand	32966238	6593	3958	1099	330	275	188	66	6	24	21
22	Orissa	41947358	8389	6688	1398	1279	349	231	84	22	30	32
23	Chhattisgarh	25540196	5108	4776	851	716	213	143	51	17	18	17
24	Madhya Pradesh	72597565	14519	8869	2420	1155	605	333	145	56	50	50
25	Gujarat	60383628	12076	7274	2013	1096	503	290	121	00	26	00
26	Daman & Diu	242911	48	26	8	03	2	02	1	0	2	2
27	Dadra & Nagar Haveli	342853	68	50	11	06	3	01	1	0	1	1
28	Maharashtra	112372972	22474	10580	3745	1816	936	365	225	80	35	23
29	Andhra Pradesh	84665533	16933	12522	2822	1570	705	167	169	58	23	17
30	Karnataka	61130704	12226	8143	2037	2193	509	325	122	146	30	27

31	Goa	1457723	291	172	48	19	12	05	3	0	2	2
32	Lakshadweep #	64429	21	14	3	04	1	01	1	0	1	2
33	Kerala	33387677	6677	4575	1113	813	278	233	67	39	14	0
34	Tamil Nadu	72138958	14427	8706	2405	1283	601	256	144	232	32	39
35	Puducherry	1244464	248	53	41	24	10	03	2	0	4	0
36	Andaman & Nicobar Islands#	379944	126	114	19	19	05	04	1	0	3	3

* Required; ** Existing; # Hilly tribal areas

Table 2: Public health workforce required in the country

S. No.	Workforce	Required	S. No.	Workforce	Required
01	Hospital superintendent	3631	41	Dietician	3631
02	Medical specialist	9684	42	PFT technician	1211
03	General Surgeon	19766	43	OT technician	10082
04	Physician	10082	44	Counselor	13713
05	Orthopedic an	4842	45	Cyto technician	1211
06	Dermatologist	3631	46	Lady Health Visitor	31457
07	Ophthalmologist	4842	47	Public health nurse	10082
08	Obstetrician & Gynecologist	22188	48	Nurse	407440
09	Pediatrics	19766	49	Sister in charge	12100
10	Anesthetist	20977	50	General duty workers/ hospital attendants	50840
11	Radiologist	4842	51	Sanitary worker	18165
12	Radiotherapist	1211	52	ANM	488888
13	PMR specialist	1211	53	Health workers	282354
14	Microbiologist	1211	54	Health assistants	80664
15	Eye surgeon	12502	55	Ophthalmic assistants	54045
16	ENT surgeon	1211	56	Dental assistant	16133
17	Dental Surgeon	14924	57	Dental technician/hygienist	7262
18	General Duty Medical Officer	106492	58	Matron	3631
19	Part-time Cancer Surgeon/Physician	10082	59	Assistant matron	1211
20	Pathologist	4842	60	Rehabilitation worker	57676
21	Pathologist cum blood bank in charge	1211	61	Clerk	80664
22	Psychiatrist	3631	62	Data handler	62916
23	Clinical psychologist	1211	63	Laboratory technician	87522
24	General Duty Medical Officer of AYUSH	10082	64	Dresser	20164
25	Specialist of AYUSH	57676	65	Ward boys	50410
26	Forensic officer	3631	66	Sweepers	50410
27	Public health Manager	13713	67	Chowkidars	50410
28	Physiotherapist/ OT	4842	68	Dhobi	10082
29	Rehabilitation therapist	1211	69	Mali	10082

30	Prosthetics	1211	70	Aya	50410
31	Orthotics	1211	71	OPD attendant	10082
32	Accounts manager	50414	72	Registration Clerk	20164
33	Pharmacist	88733	73	Peon	20164
34	Radiographer	31057	74	Driver	70578
35	Radiotherapy technician	2422	75	Cold chain and logistics assistant	54045
36	Darkroom assistant	1211	76	Psychiatric social worker/ medical social worker	1211
37	ECG technician	3631	77	Instructor for young hearing-impaired	1211
38	ECHO technician	1211	78	Plumber	1211
39	Audiometric an	1211	79	Cold chain handler	1211
40	Audiometric technician	2420	80	Class IV	161328

Table 1: Deficiencies in the number of facilities

S. No.	Staff	Existing	S. No.	Staff	Existing
1.	Doctors	25870	10.	Radiographers	1817
2.	Surgeons	1531	11.	Pharmacist	21688
3.	Ayush	8900	12.	Lab Technician	15094
4.	O & G	1939	13.	BEE	3063
5.	Physician	1165	14.	Nursing staff	58450
7.	Pediatrician	1311	15.	Health workers	244231
8.	Specialists	6781	16.	Health assistants	33599
9.	GDMO	9933			

Sources: *RHS Bulletin 2009*

References:

- GOI, MOHFW. "Mission documents on NRHM 2005-12." *Ministry of health and family welfare, Govt. of India*. April 2005. www.mohfw.nic.in/nrhm (accessed May 2010).
- MOHFW. "IPHS_for_SUBCENTRES.pdf" *Ministry of health and family welfare, Government of India*. 2006. www.mohfw.nic.in (accessed June 7, 2009).
- MOHFW. "IPHS_for_PHC.pdf" *Ministry of health and family welfare, Government of India*. 2006. www.mohfw.nic.in (accessed June 7, 2009).
- MOHFW. "IPHS_for_DH.pdf" *Ministry of health and family welfare, Government of India*. 2006. www.mohfw.nic.in (accessed June 7, 2009).
- MOHFW. "IPHS for 51 to 100 bedded with Comments of Sub-group" *Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India*. 2007. www.mohfw.nic.in (accessed June 7, 2009).
- Ministry of Health & FW, Government of India "Rural Health Survey Bulletins" 2006, 2008"
- Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Govt. of India "MIS on NRHM 2010".
- Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Govt. of India "Reports of Common review mission (CRMs)". www.mohfw.nic.in/crms (accessed July 2010).
- "New cadre in the health sector of the country." *All India Applied Sociology Subject Association*. 2010. www.aissa.co.in (accessed 2010).
- Sharma, Rohan. *The country needs an additional seven lakh doctors*. Reviews, New-Delhi: All India Applied Sociology Subject Association, 2010.
- "Training strategy under NRHM." *Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, govt. of India*. 2009. www.mohfw.nic.in/nrhm (accessed 2010).
